

Assessment of the Influence of the Thermal Properties of the Grout Backfill Material on the Heat Exchange Process of Geothermal Boreholes

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a numerical study of the heat transfer process in a vertical borehole with a simple U-tube heat exchanger. The main goal of the study is to assess the influence of the PCM enhanced (phase change material) grout material properties in the performance of the geothermal heat pump system. The simulations were developed for two cases: a Base case with a commercial grout backfill material and a case with a grout backfill material enhanced with PCM. The simulations were developed for the heating mode for a 24 hours period. A typical profile of extracted heat from the geothermal borehole, for residential heating, was set for both cases. The simulations were performed with the Ansys Fluent 16 code using the melting/solidification model. Based on the CFD results the time evolution of the heat transfer fluid temperature throughout the borehole, the heat transfer rate in the boundary between the ground and the borehole and in the U-tube surface, were analyzed. Despite the short period time considered in the simulations, the numerical results clearly have showed that enhancing the grout backfill material with PCM can improve the over all performance of the geothermal system. The PCM stabilizes the temperature inside the geothermal borehole and, as consequence, the heat transfer process in the geothermal heat pump evaporator occurs at a higher temperature level.

INTRODUCTION

Ground source heat pumps (GSHPs) are ones of the most clean and energy efficient systems for buildings climatization. In the last years the installed capacity of shallow geothermal systems have been rising, only in the European Union, geothermal heat pumps provided around 1400 ktoe in 2011 Lenhard and Malcho (2013). The most common borehole heat exchangers of GSHPs are closed loops of plastic tubes that can be disposed vertically or horizontally. In the horizontal configuration the loops are slightly below the earth's surface in backfilled trenches, this configuration is common where ample ground area is available Stuart et al (2013). In vertical systems heat exchange pipes are deeply buried, the depth of vertical wells goes from 40 to 200 m, Zeng et al. (2003), typically with diameter of 150-200 mm. In multiple wells system, the space between boreholes is around 5–6 m in order to prevent interference between adjacent boreholes and changes on the ground conditions. In vertical geothermal boreholes U-type heat exchangers, diameters with 32 or 42 mm, are the most common. A vertical borehole can have one or two pairs of such tubes in a simple-U or double-U arrangement. Comparatively to the horizontal configuration, vertical systems have the advantages of reducing the installation area and locates the pipes deep in the ground, where the temperature is constant year-round, allowing a consistent heat pump performance. The main disadvantage of vertical system is the installation costs, since drilling is normally more costly than horizontal trenching Stuart et al. (2013).

The performance of ground source heat pumps depends strongly on the heat transfer between the soil and the

borehole heat exchangers, which are closely related with the solid properties, generally, for a soil with low hydraulic conductivity, the heat transfer process is dominated by heat conduction. On the contrary, for a soil with high hydraulic conductivity, the heat transfer process is inherently coupled with heat conduction and heat advection by groundwater flow Lenhard and Malcho (2013). Other important factors that affects the performance of geothermal boreholes is the thermal resistance between the soil and the heat exchanger tubes. To ensure optimal heat transfer between the soil and the tubes, the gap between the pipes and the borehole wall are filled with grout backfill material. Over the years the industry has developed grout materials with high thermal conductivity with the objective of increasing the performance of geothermal systems by minimizing the thermal resistance between the heat exchanger tubes and the ground.

Another approach that can potentially improve the performance of geothermal borehole systems is enhancing the grout material with PCM, with the objective of stabilizing the temperature inside the borehole, taking advantage of the energy that can be stored in the liquid/solid latent heat of the PCM. Such materials are ideal for thermal energy management, because when the PCM solidifies it releases large amounts of energy in the form of latent heat of fusion, or energy of crystallization, when the PCM is melted it absorbs a similar amount of energy.

Nowadays, there are different types of PCMs on the market and in different forms including encapsulated in powder particles. The solid particles can have different sizes and independent on the phase of the PCM liquid/solid in the particles, the powder particles are always solid, which presents some advantages comparatively to non-encapsulated PCMs. Powder encapsulated PCMs can be mixed with common building materials in order to enhance its thermal properties Kalnaes and jelle (2015).

This work presents numerical simulations of the heat transfer process in a vertical geothermal borehole with the objective of study the influence of enhancing the grout material with PCM on the performance of GSHPs. The simulations were developed for a case with a commercial grout backfill material and a case with a grout backfill material enhanced with PCM. A typical profile of extracted heat from the geothermal borehole for residential heating was set for both cases.

CASES STUDIED AND COMPUTATIONAL DETAILS

Computational domain

The geometry study is a conventional vertical borehole with a simple U-tube heat exchanger. The borehole is 60 m deep and 150 mm diameter, the heat exchanger is a simple U-tube probe with 42 mm diameter, Figure 1 presents the geometry studied.

Figure 1 Geothermal borehole geometry.

Due to the symmetry of the geometry, the simulations were developed in a half-cylindrical computational domain, with a total length of 60 m and an external diameter of 4 m. The borehole is in the center of the computational domain, the annular volume between the borehole border and the external diameter of the computational domain represents the ground, the borehole is filled with grout backfill material, the U-tube probe is made of high density polyethylene (HDP) and a mixture of water and glycol was considered as heat transport fluid (HTF). Table 1 presents the properties of the materials used in the CFD simulations. The bulk values of the density, thermal capacity and thermal conductivity of the PCM enhanced grout material were considered equal to the commercial grout material, and for the bulk value of the latent heat was 20 kJ/kg. Which represents a mass fraction of encapsulated PCM in the grout mixture of 0.15 for a powder encapsulated PCM with a density of 1250 kg/m³ and a latent heat of 150 kJ/kg.

Table 1. Material Properties

Property	HTF	HDP	Soil	Grout backfill material	PCM enhanced Grout backfill material
ρ [kg/m ³]	1033	950	1400	1400	1400
C_p [J/kg*K]	3930	2000	1260	1250	1250
k [W/m*K]	0.47	0.42	2.2	2.0	2.0
α [m ² /s]	1.16 E-7	2.21 E-7	9.57*E-6	1.14*E-6	1.14*E-6
Latent heat [kJ/kg]	-	-	-	-	20
Solidus Temperature [°C]	-	-	-	-	13
Liquidus temperature [°C]	-	-	-	-	15

The model was built in a 3D grid with approximately 700000 quadrilateral elements; the mesh is finer in the borehole region. Figure 2 presents a detail view of the computational mesh. In the longitudinal direction the mesh has 60 elements with the size of one meter. The Soil volume mesh has 80 no-uniform elements along the radial direction and in the U-tube and the borehole zone the element size, in the radial plan of the mesh, is two and three millimeters, respectively.

Figure 2 Detail view of the mesh used in the CFD simulations.

Mathematical Model

The numerical simulations were done with the aid of Ansys Fluent 16.0. The numerical code solves the mass,

momentum and energy transport equations for constant density. The turbulence was modelled by the two equations k-epsilon of standard model and the energy equation was solved in the form of total enthalpy.

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{v} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial t} + \rho \nabla \cdot (\vec{v} \vec{v}) = -\nabla p + \mu \{ [\nabla \vec{v} + \nabla \vec{v}^T] \} \quad (2)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} + \rho \nabla \cdot (\vec{v} H) = \nabla \cdot (k \nabla T) \quad (3)$$

v represents the velocity, ρ the density, μ the dynamic viscosity, k the thermal conductivity, T de temperature and H de total enthalpy defined as:

$$H = h + \Delta H \quad (4)$$

$$h = h_{ref} + \int_{T_{ref}}^T c_p dT \quad (5)$$

h represents the sensible enthalpy, C_p the specific heat and ΔH the phase change enthalpy. To simulate melting/solidification process the software uses a mathematical formulations based on the enthalpy-porosity technique. The temperature is calculated through the total enthalpy and the liquid mass fraction, γ , defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma &= 0 && \text{if, } T < T_{solidus} \\ \gamma &= \frac{T - T_{solidus}}{T_{liquidus} - T_{solidus}} && \text{if, } T_{solidus} < T < T_{liquidus} \\ \gamma &= 1 && \text{if, } T_{liquidus} < T \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

locally, the phase change enthalpy can be expressed in terms of the liquid mass fraction and the material latent heat, L , as: $\Delta H = \gamma L$.

Computational details

The simulations were performed for 24 hours with a time step of one second, for a heating mode operation of the geothermal system. The average temperature of the soil was 17 °C and the HTF mass flow rate was 0.32 kg/s. For both simulations the amount of the heat removed from the geothermal borehole over the time is present in Figure 3. At each time instant the inlet temperature of the HTF into the borehole was calculated based on the HP evaporator energy balance, expressed by equation (7).

$$T_{inlet}^t = T_{outlet}^{t-1} - \frac{\dot{Q}}{\dot{m} \cdot C_p} \quad (7)$$

The simulations convergence criterion was 10^{-6} for the residuals of the mass, momentum, and turbulence equations

and 10^{-12} for the solution of the energy equation.

Figure 3 Heat transfer rate extracted from the borehole over the time.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4 shows the temperature distribution in the computational domain at the 20 hours time instant. The results presented in Figure 4 clearly show that the heat transfer process occurs essentially along the radial direction and the main temperature gradients are in the Borehole region. The data of Figure 4 are from the Base case simulations the results of the PCM case are qualitatively similar and are not presented here.

Figure 4 Temperature distribution at 20 hours (Base case).

Figure 5 presents the temperature radial distribution at 30 m deep, for both simulations, at two time instants (12 and 24 hours). The temperature radial profiles indicate that the temperature gradients are restricted to the central region of the computational domain; at the external boundary the temperature gradient is zero, which proves that the dimension of the computational domain is appropriate to perform the simulations. These results also show that, for both cases, the influence in the ground temperature of extracted heat from the borehole, increases as process progress. At 12 hours, the temperature radial profile is the same for both simulations, however at 24 hours the temperature near the center of the borehole is higher for the Base case comparatively to the PCM case.

Figure 5 Temperature radial profiles at 12 and 24 hours (30 m deep)

To better understand the influence of the enhancement of the grout backfill with PCM on the performance of the geothermal borehole system Figure 6 presents the time profiles of the temperature in two control points at 30 m deep, Point A at the center of the borehole and Point B located at the borehole boundary (see Figure 4). Figure 7 presents the time profiles of the borehole HTF inlet and outlet temperatures, Figure 8 presents the time profile of the PCM average liquid mass fraction and Figure 9 shows the heat transfer rate to the HTF through the U-tube and the heat transfer rate from the soil to the borehole, for both simulations.

Figure 6 Temperature time profiles at point A and B (30 m deep).

Figure 7 HTF inlet and outlet temperature time profiles.

Figure 8 Average PCM liquid mass fraction time profile.

The results show that enhancing the backfill material with PCM can improve the performance of the whole geothermal system. As is shown in Figure 6, in general, the temperature at points A and B is higher in the PCM case comparatively to Base case. The borehole inlet and outlet temperatures of the HTF, presented in Figure 7, are also higher for the PCM case, which indicates that the heat transfer process to the heat pump (HP) evaporator occurs at higher temperatures, improving the efficiency of the heat pump. Figure 6 also shows that over the first 7:50 hours the temperature at points A and B presents the same time evolution, for both cases. However, after that instant, the temperature profiles of both simulations are different. In the PCM case when the temperature locally decreases below the PCM liquidus temperature, the PCM solidifies, and releases latent energy which stabilizes the temperature inside the borehole. On the other hand, at the end of the simulations, when heat extracted from the borehole becomes very low and finally stops, the temperature at points A and B, for the Base case becomes superior to the PCM case. After the 19 hours, the energy balance between the heat received from the soil and extracted by the HTF becomes positive and the temperature inside the borehole starts to increase. When the temperature locally rises above the PCM solidus temperature, the solid PCM starts to melt back, storing energy. As a consequence the temperature rising is slower for the PCM case comparatively to the Base case. This process is clearly illustrated by the time profile of the average PCM liquid mass fraction inside the borehole presented in Figure 8. For the PCM case the time evolution of the temperature inside the borehole depends on the balance of the energy that is extracted by the HTF, the conduction of heat from the soil to the borehole and the energy that is released/stored by the PCM melting/solidification process.

Finally, the results presented on Figure 9 clearly show the effect of adding PCM to the backfill material on the heat transfer rates in the geothermal borehole. When the PCM solidifies, to transfer the same amount of energy to the HTF, the heat transfers rate from the soil to the borehole is lower for the PCM case comparatively to the Base case. On the other hand, when the PCM melts back, the heat transfer rate from the soil to the borehole is higher for the PCM case comparatively to the Base case.

Figure 9 Heat transfer rate from the borehole to the HTF and from the ground to the borehole.

CONCLUSION

In this work the heat transfer process was studied in a vertical geothermal borehole with a simple U-tube heat exchanger using a numerical simulation tool (Ansys 16). The simulations were developed for a Base case with a commercial grout backfill material and a case with a grout backfill material enhanced with PCM. The simulations were developed for the heating mode for a period of 24 hours. The same profile of extracted energy from the geothermal borehole was set for both cases. Despite the short period time considered in the simulations, the CFD results indicates that:

- enhancing the backfill material with PCM stabilizes the temperature inside the geothermal borehole at a higher level when heat is extracted from the geothermal borehole;
- the heat transfer process occurs at higher temperatures in geothermal HP evaporator for the PCM case comparatively to the Base case;
- enhancing the grout backfill material of a geothermal borehole with PCM can improve the performance of whole geothermal system.

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